

Corn leaf disease identification

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Abstract— The proposed project aims to develop a model that uses machine learning algorithms and the Yolov7 to accurately identify corn leaf diseases. This model will allow users to upload images of corn leaves and receive a diagnosis of the type of disease present. The system will be trained using a pre-labeled dataset of corn leaf images to ensure high accuracy. The use of machine learning algorithms will enable this model to identify even subtle differences in leaf appearance that may indicate a specific disease. This model will provide farmers and agricultural experts with a quick and accurate tool for identifying crop diseases, helping them make informed decisions about crop management and reducing the risk of crop failure.

Keywords— Yolov7, Machine learning, Corn leaf disease

Introduction

In a variety of applications, including disease detection, soil monitoring, weed control, identifying pests, computer vision and drones for crop analysis, and weather forecasting, the agriculture sector is embracing artificial intelligence and machine learning. The Indian economy's most significant sector, accounting for 18 percentage of its GDP, is agriculture. Agriculture is the primary source of income for a sizable portion of India's people. India is hence heavily reliant on crop productivity. In India, corn is a widely grown crop. Due to its great export potential and dependence on by a sizable community of farmers, corn growing is crucial in India. Corn is used in many businesses, including those that produce food and beverages, poultry, and animal feed. With a global production that surpasses that of wheat and rice, it has emerged as a staple food in many regions of the world. However, India's maize production is almost half that of the world as a whole. The fact that maize is susceptible to numerous diseases, which drastically lower crop yields overall, is one of the causes of its low yield. In addition to being a popular ingredient in cereals, corn is also used to make ethanol, animal feed, corn syrup, and starch. Certain leaf diseases continue to pose a problem for agricultural production, reducing not only the crop yield but also its nutritional content. Common rust, grey leaf spot, and leaf

blight are a few of the common leaf diseases. In their early stages, many leaf diseases may resemble one another quite closely, making it exceedingly challenging to identify with the unaided eye. Visual inspection of leaf diseases requires a team of experts and ongoing crop monitoring. Thus, making it very costly, time-consuming and less reliable. In recent years, advances in machine learning algorithms and computer vision have made it possible to develop automated systems for the identification of crop diseases. The Yellow v7 dataset is a publicly available dataset containing a large number of images of corn leaves affected by various diseases. This dataset provides an excellent opportunity to train machine learning algorithms to identify specific corn leaf diseases. This project proposes the development of a model that utilizes the Yellow v7 dataset and machine learning algorithms to accurately identify corn leaf diseases. This model will provide a user-friendly interface that allows farmers and agricultural experts to upload images of corn leaves and receive an accurate diagnosis of the disease present. The system will be trained using the pre-labeled Yellow v7 dataset to ensure high accuracy. The use of machine learning algorithms will enable the model to identify even subtle differences in leaf appearance that may indicate a specific disease. The model's potential impact is significant, as it will provide farmers with a quick and accurate tool for identifying crop diseases, helping them make informed decisions about crop management and reducing the risk of crop failure. This project has the potential to contribute to global food security by improving the management and control of corn crop diseases.

I. SCOPE OF THE PROJECT

A reliable supply of wholesome food for the world's expanding population depends on precision agricultural technologies. A significant portion of crops are lost each year as a result of pests and diseases, which continue to pose a serious danger. Crop health may be automatically determined from photographs, enabling timely management to boost production and lower input costs. One of the biggest problems in the agricultural industry is crop diseases. Traditional methods for diagnosing crop diseases are inefficient in terms of time and money, and the rate of

misdiagnosis is very significant. Additionally, incorrect disease identification lowers agricultural output effectiveness and heightens economic loss. The deep neural network demonstrated notable results in the early days of machine learning and enabled researchers to increase the precision of object identification and recognition systems. A reliable supply of wholesome food for the world's expanding population depends on precision agricultural technologies. A significant portion of crops are lost each year as a result of pests and diseases, which continue to pose a serious danger. Automated crop health detection from photos aids in prompt response to boost yield while helping reduce input cost. The performance of the agriculture sector is one of the key variables that determines a country's economic strength. Maintaining the health of any crop is essential to ensuring its quality and yield since crops can contract a variety of diseases. Studying agricultural diseases is essential for scientific activity and research because crops are one of the primary sources of sustenance. Recent studies have demonstrated how quickly illnesses can impact plants. The scope of a model that utilizes the Yellow v7 dataset and machine learning algorithms to identify corn leaf diseases is significant. This model can provide an effective tool for the early detection and accurate identification of diseases affecting corn crops, enabling farmers and agricultural experts to make informed decisions about crop management. Some potential areas of scope for the project include:

1. Developing a user-friendly interface that allows users to easily upload images of corn leaves and receive an accurate diagnosis of the disease present.
2. Integrating machine learning algorithms trained on the Yellow v7 dataset to accurately identify specific corn leaf diseases, including common and rare diseases.
3. Providing information and resources on the various corn leaf diseases identified by the system, including their causes, symptoms, and management strategies.
4. Incorporating a database of previously diagnosed corn leaf diseases to enable the system to learn from past diagnoses and improve its accuracy over time.
4. Enabling the system to provide recommendations for disease management and prevention based on the identified disease, including appropriate treatment options and crop management practices. The model's potential impact is significant, as it can improve the management and control of corn crop diseases, helping to reduce the risk of crop failure and improve global food security. The scope of the project can be expanded in the future to include other 6 crops and diseases, further improving the effectiveness and usefulness of the system

LITERATURE SURVEY

Recent advancements in smart device technology can be used to automatically diagnose corn disease and reduce crop losses. This study describes a real-time technique for detecting corn leaf disease based on deep convolutional neural networks. On a system with GPU, the performance of deep neural networks can be increased by altering the pooling combinations and hyper-parameters. Additionally, the created model's parameter count is tuned to make it acceptable for real-time inference. The creation of deep learning-based models like CNN, which can automatically learn features, has been the main focus of recent research. The three prevalent diseases of

maize leaves—gray spot, leaf spot, and rust—can be accurately diagnosed using a method based on K-means clustering and an upgraded deep learning model, according to a recent paper. In order to identify three diseases, sample photos will first be clustered using the K-means technique before being fed into the upgraded deep learning model. The influence of various k values—2, 4, 8, 16, 32, and 64—and models—VGG-16, ResNet18, Inception v3, VGG-19, and the improved deep learning model—on the detection of corn disease is examined in the paper.

II. METHODOLOGY

The YOLOv7 algorithm is making big waves in the computer vision and machine learning communities. In this article, we will provide the basics of how YOLOv7 works and what makes it the best object detector algorithm available today. The newest YOLO algorithm surpasses all previous object detection models and YOLO versions in both speed and accuracy. It requires several times cheaper hardware than other neural networks and can be trained much faster on small datasets without any pre-trained weights. Hence, YOLOv7 is expected to become the industry standard for object detection in the near future, surpassing the previous state-of-the-art for real-time applications (YOLO v4).

3.2 Advantages

In computer vision, real-time object detection is a very important task that is often a key component in computer vision systems. Applications that use real-time object detection models include video analytics, robotics, autonomous vehicles, multi-object tracking and object counting, medical image analysis, and so on. An object detector is an object detection algorithm that performs image recognition tasks by taking an image as input and then predicting bounding boxes and class probabilities for each object in the image. One of the main advantages of YOLO v7 is its speed. It can process images at a rate of 155 frames per second, much faster than other state-of-the-art object detection algorithms. Even the original baseline YOLO model was capable of processing at a maximum rate of 45 frames per second.

YOLO algorithm takes an image as input and then uses a simple deep convolutional neural network to detect objects in the image.

Data visualization is improved by TensorFlow's graphical approach. Additionally, it enables simple node debugging with Tensor Board. By doing so, the neural network is successfully resolved with less effort than visiting the entire code. Due to TensorFlow's interoperability with Keras, users can program various areas of high-level functionality in it. TensorFlow benefits from Keras' system-specific functionality, including eager execution, estimators, and pipelining. The inputs, outputs, and layer combinations supported by the Keras functional API are numerous. Using this platform, you can conduct almost any operation. TensorFlow's ability to be installed on any machine and its graphical model representation allow its users to create any form of system

III. CONCLUSION

The project highlights the importance of sustainable farming practices by reducing the use of pesticides and herbicides and

leading to healthier crops and improved yields. The model can help farmers save time and money by detecting diseases early and preventing their spread. In conclusion, the project demonstrates the application of deep learning techniques in agriculture and highlights the potential for using technology to address challenges in sustainable farming practices. The model for detecting corn leaf disease using YoloV7 algorithm can benefit farmers by providing them with timely and accurate information on disease detection and contribute towards sustainable farming practices.

IV. LIMITATIONS

The model will currently identify the corn disease that is currently having the greatest impact, which is either corn leaf blight, corn grey leaf spot, or maize common rust. We are unsure of how many diseases will affect our harvest negatively in the future. Only when we update those bits of information once every six months will this model be able to make an accurate prediction. It is a significant project restriction. Since we use 30 picture data and can store all of the data in a database, this procedure uses NoSQL.

V. FUTURE WORKS

It is currently only a model. It will eventually be made into an application that farmers and others working in the industry can use. It is possible to create an automated method for it. From the dataset until the final outcome, the entire process will be automated. After the application is created, users will update the dataset on their own. Because we employ picture data throughout the entire process, once a user checks a leaf using photos, the images are automatically saved in a database, in this case a NoSQL database. Here, we just

employ three diseases, but in the future, we will be able to classify any illnesses that may negatively affect our agricultural sector. Currently, we just deal with maize leaves, but in the future, we will need to add a variety of crop items to this application.

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